

CONSEQUENCE OF COSMETICS USE ON FEMALES HEALTH & ITS REMEDIES

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ABSTRACT

Cosmetics are applied to the body to clean, enhance, make more appealing, or alter appearance. They might contain a wide range of active substances that are extremely dangerous, especially when used over an extended period of time, like steroids, hydroquinone, and mercury. If we consider the frequency of application, the duration of practise, and the area of the body applied, many of these components are unhealthy and pose health hazards. Cosmetics are causing alarming adverse events to its users. There are a number of potential adverse effects of cosmetic use on women's health. These include skin irritations, allergic reactions, and potentially harmful chemicals being absorbed through the skin. Cosmetics can also harbor bacteria and

fungi, which can lead to infections. In some cases, cosmetics may also interfere with the body's natural hormone production. Several strategies exist to lessen the possibility of negative cosmetic impacts. These include using products that are hypoallergenic and non-comedogenic, avoiding products that contain known irritants or allergens, and using products that are water-based rather than oil-based. It is also important to properly cleanse the skin before and after using cosmetics, and to avoid sharing products with others.

KEYWORDS: Cosmetics, Health, Beautification.

INTRODUCTION

Cosmetics are described as "products for beautifying, cleansing, or modifying bodily appearance" by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA).^[1] Cosmetics are substances used to clean, enhance, encourage attractiveness, or otherwise change the look of the human body. They can be administered to the body in a variety of ways, such as by rubbing, pouring,

sprinkling, spraying, inserting, and more. Skin moisturisers, lipsticks, nail polishes, eye and face makeup preparations, cleaning shampoos, permanent waves, hair dyes, medicinal soaps, deodorants, and anything made to be utilised as a component in a cosmetic product are all covered by this term.^[2] Cosmetics have been a significant part of daily life in all periods and have a variety of uses. The Saudi FDA defines a cosmetic as any item with one or more ingredients that is meant to be used to the exterior of the human body, including the skin, hair, nails, lips, teeth, and mucous lining of the mouth, for cleansing, perfume, protecting or keeping in good condition, altering or improving look, or altering or improving the body's odour.^[3]

Cosmetics can enhance a person's perception of their beauty, but they can also have unfavourable outcomes. Various cosmetic products have been linked to these side effects for a variety of reasons, including sensitivity to particular ingredients or the product's formulation, microbial contamination of the product, misuse as a result of poor labelling, infractions involving colour additives, and also particular cosmetic ingredients like fragrances and preservatives that contain risky or harmful substances. The leading causes of consumer exposure to toxicity, according to some research, are several chemicals and their combined effects in cosmetic items.^[4-6]

Numerous additional negative reactions have also been connected to cosmetics, such as pigment issues, irritants, contact urticaria, photosensitization, harm to the hair and nails, and outbreaks similar to acne.^[7]

According to statistics, the typical woman uses 12 personal care products per day that include 168 different chemicals. According to a recent study, the skin can take in up to 60% of the toxins present in the objects it comes into touch with. Another investigation by the Evanston, Illinois-based North western University School of Medicine revealed that from 2015 to 2016, complaints concerning cosmetics more than doubled.^[8]

The main causes of this underestimation Especially because users were unable to notice or pay attention to little and moderately harmful occurrences, self-medication, self-diagnosis, and lack of medical counsel are among the dangers.^[9]

Remedies

Developing nations like Ethiopia do not require marketing authorization for cosmetics, in contrast to the majority of western nations, which have laws and regulations governing the safety and labelling of cosmetics.^[10]

Due to the nation's high prevalence of illiteracy, weak laws, and geographical climate, More interactions between topically applied cosmetics and UV radiation are to be anticipated.^[9-10]

The public's protection from the negative consequences of these products is not given much consideration by the drug regulatory system, as is also the case in many other nations.^[11-15]

Using Cosmetics Safely Guideline: To stay clean and improve their appearance, people utilise cosmetics. These products include lipstick, nail paint, deodorant, hairspray, shampoo, shower gel, tattoo ink, hair adhesives, hair removal tools, and hair colours, as well as the majority of soaps, some tooth whitening solutions, and a variety of cleansing wipes. Use of cosmetics must be done so safely. Use all cosmetics items in accordance with safety precautions:^[17]

- ❖ Examine the label. Pay attention to all instructions and warnings.
- ❖ Hands should be washed before using the product.
- ❖ Do not exchange cosmetics.
- ❖ When not in use, keep the containers clean, properly closed, and away from excessive temperatures.
- ❖ If cosmetics alter in colour or scent, discard them.
- ❖ Use spray cans or aerosols only in well-ventilated locations. Use caution when using them around open flames or when smoking. It might cause a fire.
- ❖ Avoid putting saliva or water in your mascara. Germs could be added.

CONCLUSIONS

Numerous ingredients have been used in cosmetics, skin care products, Since ancient times, cosmetics for the body, hair, and nails have been available. Some chemicals, such as preservatives, stabilisers, mineral pigments, dyes, and shine, were added to these items to improve their quality and enhance their effects. Some of these compounds may also have adverse impacts on human health, such as allergic reactions and irritation. Due of the more than 10,000 components in cosmetic and aesthetic products that have been related to disease, they are not particularly healthy. The continued uses of cosmetics exposes people to risky

side effects such contact dermatitis, allergies, skin rashes, type IV hypersensitivity, and other ailments. The general public should be informed that cosmetic products include dangerous ingredients. Applying a global cosmeto-vigilance is crucial to advancing the creation, marketing, and broad public use of cosmetic products. In order to prevent the hazards connected with the use of cosmetics from becoming a significant public health issue, this public health approach provides a reliable way to learn about the safety of cosmetic products and their contents.

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